

Management Strategies for Soil Compaction in Mechanized Sugarcane Cultivation

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Received Date: 23-Mar-2021

Accepted Date: 28-Apr-2021

Published Date: 30-June-2021

Abstract

A field survey was carried out at Cuddalore and Villupuram districts of Tamil Nadu State to assess the impact of continues mechanisation in sugarcane cultivation on soil physical properties during 2016 -17. Soil samples were taken at different depths viz., 0-20, 20-40 and 40-60 cm's from mechanized sugarcane harvested fields as well as nearby non mechanised fields as control. The results showed that an increased bulk density, hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate in mechanized cultivation field soils particularly at deeper depths (20 – 40 cm) and (40 – 60 cm) implying mechanization induced soil compaction. To develop a suitable management strategy, field experiments were conducted at Sugarcane Research Station, Cuddalore during 2017-20 in a field where mechanized sugarcane cultivation was followed continuously for four years in a non -saline neutral sandy loam (0-15cm) and clay (15 – 60 cm) soil with the sugarcane variety CoC 25 under strip plot design in three replications. The main plot treatments of chisel plough, double disc plough and conventional ploughing in combination with the sub plot treatments of farm yard manure, composted coirpith, pressmud, green manure and composted sugarcane trash incorporation.

In both the plant and ratoon crops of sugarcane the result revealed that, among the tillages, chisel plough registered its efficiency of breaking the compaction and significantly recorded the maximum values of millable canes, individual cane weight, cane length, cane girth, number of internodes, length of internode and cane yield and the juice quality such as brix, pole, purity, CCS and sugar yield. Comparing the different sources of organics, FYM application @ 12.5 t ha⁻¹ recorded significantly lesser bulk density, particle density and penetrometer resistance and higher the porosity, HC and IR which in turn reflected in significantly higher values of varied sugarcane crop biometrics, juice quality parameters in both plant and ratoon crops. Regarding cost benefit ratio while, the chisel plough recorded the maximum of 2.83 and 3.46 in plant and ratoon crop respectively, the farm yard manure 12.5 @ t/ha incorporation recorded 2.87 in plant crop 3.04 in ratoon crop. Among the treatment combinations, chisel ploughing with farm yard manure @ 12.5 t/ha application registered its superiority in reducing the bulk density, particle density and penetrometer resistance and increasing the porosity, HC and IR compared to other treatments and their by recorded significantly higher growth and yield parameters viz., tillers (1,49,100/ha), millable cane (1,46,110/ha), individual cane weight (2.55 kg), cane girth (3.49 cm), cane length (348.46 cm), number of nodes (28.4), inter node length (12.6 cm) and cane yield (143.3 t/ha). The same combination recorded higher values of quality parameters viz., brix (23.73 %), pole (18.98 %), purity (84.35 %), CCS (12.47 %), sugar yield (17.88 t/ha) and B: C ratio (4.22).

Key words: Soil compaction, Sugarcane mechanisation, Mechanised harvest, Subsoil ploughing, Organic amendments Soil structure, Bulk density, Particle density, Hydraulic conductivity, water infiltration rate and Root dry biomass.

Introduction

The practice of land preparation for sugarcane cultivation is already being completely mechanised, where as other operations such as planting, weeding, earthingup, fertilization, spraying and harvesting are now being increasingly carried out by machineries and implements. Cutting cane by hand is hard physical work carried out mostly under hot and unpleasant weather conditions. It is not normally considered as an ideal job, if alternative works with attractive percentages are available and in many countries cane cutters are with low social status. Cane cutter's shortages often occur at national and global level of industrialisation which develops easier or better paid work become available (Ng Cheong *et al.*, 2009). Based on these experiences, the search for a satisfactory cane harvesting machinery was started over 100 years ago and huge amount of time and ingenuity have been devoted, particularly by Australian cane farmers (Glyn James, 2004). Mechanical harvesting is currently dominated by combined cut/chop/load harvesters in most of the areas of the cane growing countries. From the view of sprouting ratoon crops, manual cutting is always preferable to mechanical cutting since, harvesting machines cause more damage to the cane stools and the risk of soil compaction is much higher.

Soil damage resulting from the heavy machineries can be reduced through adopting of continuous working of preventive measures, in consideration to the most of soil and machine relationship. The magnitudes and distribution of the stresses produced in the soil through the loads carried by the axles of the machines used in sugarcane cultivation systems were analysed in detailed by Naseri *et al.*, (2007). The Tyres/Track and soil compaction (TASC) tool took the soil and machine data, estimated contact areas and mean contact pressures at the soil–tyre/truck interface, associate with pro-consolidation stress data obtained in the uniaxial test modelled the propagation of the applied stress into the soil (Wellington de Silva Guimaraes Junnyor, *et al.*, 2019). Mechanical harvesting of sugarcane is not the only cause of soil compaction, the loading vehicles traffic after conventional tillage results in soil disaggregation and promotes soil compaction, while on areas with less intensive soil tillage, and in soil with greater load bearing capacity, the stress dissipates in the surface layers (Braunack, M.V. and McGarry, D, 2006). Several studies have been performed on the effect of machines traffic in agricultural fields, which increases soil compaction on tires paths and in some cases in regions near the tracks formed by tires (Horn *et al.*, 2001; Braunack and McGarry, 2006). Tire sliding also has strong influence on the increase of soil compaction (Garside *et al.*, 2009), and soil deformation also increases with machine traffic (Sousa *et al.*, 2014).

In India sugarcane growers are increasingly resorting to mechanisation as labour is scarce and costly. Hence, appropriate strategies to eliminate or minimise occurrence of soil compaction in sugarcane production through deep tillage, which can reduce the risk associate with different operations through machineries and equipments. In the present study is conducted with two different types of aims of experimentations: first one is field survey in the machine harvesting intensive areas; to assess impact of mechanization with heavy machineries which lead to soil compaction and the second experiments to develop suitable management practices with modified tillage system and organic amendments to overcome the soil compaction.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in two phases, to evaluate the potential impact of soil physical properties due to tillage's in land preparation, planting of the sugarcane billets, intercultural operations with tractors and the mechanised harvesting traffic and to improve soil physical properties with different treatment combinations. In the first phase, survey was conducted during 2016-17 in sugarcane growing areas to assess the soil compaction due to continuous sugarcane mechanization in and around sugar factories areas of Cuddalore and Villupuram districts in Tamil Nadu, India. For mechanized sugarcane cultivation, the machineries such as tractor fitted with disc harrow, disc plough, rotovator, cultivator, power weeder, earthingup machine and mechanical harvester of 4000 and 8000 series, trash chopper with bladder, stubble shaver and ratoon manager were used by farmers in

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these study areas. The soil samples were collected from thirty different locations at three different depths (0-20, 20-40 & 40-60 cm's) both from mechanized sugarcane harvested fields as well as nearby non mechanised fields as control and analysed for soil physical properties such as bulk density, particle density, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, infiltration rate and texture (Hesse, P.R., 1971)..

In the second phase, field experiments were conducted during 2017-20in a field where mechanized sugarcane cultivation was followed continuously for four years at Sugarcane Research Station, Cuddalore with one plant and ratoon crop with sugarcane variety CoC 25 under strip plot design (Panse,V.G. and Sukhatme, P.V, 1978) in three replications. The main plot treatments consist of chisel ploughing (M₁), double disc ploughing (M₂) and conventional ploughing (M₃-Farmer's practice) and the sub plot treatmentswerefarm yard manure@ 12.5 t ha⁻¹ (S₁), composted coir-pith@ 10.0 t ha⁻¹ (S₂), sesbania green manure (*Sesbania aculeata*) @ 40.0 t ha⁻¹ in-situ incorporation (S₃), composted press-mud @ 25.0 t ha⁻¹ (S₄), and composted sugarcane trash @ 15.0 t ha⁻¹(S₅).. The fertilizers were applied @ 300:100:200 kg of N, P₂O₅ & K₂O ha⁻¹ after subtracting nutrient supply from organics and green manure in the respective treatments.

The soil of the experimental field wasnon –saline, neutral, sandy loam (0-15cm) and clay (15 – 60 cm) with low in available N, medium in available P and high in available K. The details of the Physico-chemical properties of the soil and amendments are furnished in Tables.1,2 and 3. The sugarcane crop was raised during early season planting(December -January 2017).After harvest of the plant crop, the sugarcane crop was allowed to grow for ratoon studies. All the crop management practices were adopted as per the recommendation for both plant and ratoon sugarcane crop.

Physico-chemical properties

Table1. Chemical Characteristics of Organic Manures

S.No.	Organic Source	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
1.	Farm Yard Manure	0.45	0.20	0.48
2.	Composted coir pith	1.06	0.4	1.20
3.	Green Manure in situ	2.70	0.53	2.21
4.	Press mud	0.95	1.15	0.62
5.	Composted sugarcane	0.35	0.24	0.50

Table2. Physical characteristics of the experimental soil

Parameters	Soil Depth (cm)		
	0 – 15	15 – 30	30 – 45
Soil Texture(Piper, 1966)	Sandy loam	Clay	Clay
Sand (%)	58.5	10.2	9.8
Silt (%)	23.2	27.5	27.0
Clay (%)	18.3	62.3	63.2
Bulk Density (Mg m ⁻³)	1.52	1.26	1.27
Particle Density (Mg m ⁻³)	2.69	2.73	2.77
Pore Space (%)	43.50	53.67	54.15
Soil Penetrometer reading (MPa)	0.57	2.15	2.26
Hydraulic Conductivity (cm hr ⁻¹)	1.30	0.12	0.11
Infiltration Rate (cm hr ⁻¹)	0.52		

Table 3. Chemical Characteristics of experimental soil

Parameters	Soil Depth (cm)		
	0 – 15	15 – 30	30 – 45
pH	7.1	7.2	7.2
EC (dS m ⁻¹)	0.46	0.58	0.60
Alkaline KmnO ₄ - N (kg ha ⁻¹) (Subbaiah and Asija, 1956)	168	160	158
Olsen - P (kg ha ⁻¹) (Olsen et al., 1954)	45	43	40

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NH ₄ OAc-K (kg ha ⁻¹) (Jackson, 1973)	128	145	149
Organic carbon (%) (Walkley and Black, 1934)	0.40	0.36	0.32

Result and Discussion

Experiment-I

Soil samples, both bulk and core samples were taken from the demarked survey areas at three different depths viz., 0-20, 20-40 and 40-60 cm's in continuously mechanized sugarcane harvested fields as well as nearby non mechanised fields as a control. The samples were analyzed for their texture, bulk density and hydraulic conductivity. The field infiltration rate was also assessed using double ring infiltrometer. The results are presented in the Table 4.

Table.4. Effect of mechanization on sugarcane soil physical properties

Riot No.		Depth of soil (cm)	Texture				Bulk density Mg/m ³	Hydraulic conductivity (cm/h)	Infiltration rate (mm/h)
			Sand	Silt	Clay				
1.	M	0-20	65.5	18.7	15.6	SL	1.33	5.43	15.2
		20-40	64.1	18.9	16.9	SL	1.34	5.22	
		40-60	59.5	19.5	20.9	SCL	1.36	4.92	
	C	0-20	64.2	19.5	15.9	SL	1.33	5.46	15.8
		20-40	63.8	19.2	16.8	SL	1.35	5.30	
		40-60	59.7	19.3	20.8	SCL	1.34	5.12	
2.	M	0-20	57.4	17.5	25.6	SCL	1.31	6.25	4.2
		20-40	56.8	18.1	25.1	SCL	1.33	5.94	
		40-60	53.8	19.4	26.7	SCL	1.35	5.64	
	C	0-20	56.8	18.2	24.9	SCL	1.31	6.27	4.4
		20-40	56.2	18.0	25.7	SCL	1.32	6.09	
		40-60	53.4	18.7	27.8	SCL	1.33	5.89	
3.	M	0-20	64.7	17.8	17.4	SL	1.31	6.02	16.3
		20-40	63.9	18.2	17.9	SL	1.32	5.76	
		40-60	60.7	19.5	19.8	SL	1.34	4.96	
	C	0-20	64.6	17.9	17.5	SL	1.30	6.06	17.0
		20-40	63.7	18.1	18.1	SL	1.31	5.94	
		40-60	60.9	19.7	19.3	SL	1.32	5.67	
4.	M	0-20	51.9	33.5	14.6	L	1.20	1.44	8.2
		20-40	50.3	33.9	15.8	L	1.23	1.36	
		40-60	47.8	35.2	17.0	L	1.25	1.27	
	C	0-20	52.4	33.8	13.8	L	1.20	1.43	8.7
		20-40	50.2	34.0	15.7	L	1.21	1.41	
		40-60	47.8	35.1	17.1	L	1.22	1.38	
5.	M	0-20	72.8	18.2	9.0	LS	1.32	5.65	26.4
		20-40	71.5	19.2	9.3	LS	1.34	4.23	
		40-60	69.7	20.8	9.5	LS	1.37	4.00	
	C	0-20	72.7	18.2	9.1	LS	1.32	5.65	27.0
		20-40	71.2	19.4	9.4	LS	1.33	4.36	
		40-60	47.8	35.0	9.6	LS	1.34	4.16	
6.	M	0-20	56.7	18.5	24.8	SCL	1.32	6.10	4.3
		20-40	55.5	18.9	25.6	SCL	1.34	5.82	
		40-60	53.8	19.4	26.7	SCL	1.37	5.22	
	C	0-20	56.8	18.2	24.9	SCL	1.32	6.09	4.6
		20-40	56.2	18.4	25.4	SCL	1.33	5.99	
		40-60	53.6	19.2	27.2	SCL	1.34	5.56	
7.	M	0-20	56.8	20.9	22.3	SCL	1.31	4.32	4.2
		20-40	54.8	21.8	23.4	SCL	1.32	4.09	
		40-60	53.2	22.3	24.5	SCL	1.34	4.01	
	C	0-20	56.7	21.1	22.2	SCL	1.31	4.35	4.5
		20-40	55.0	21.8	23.2	SCL	1.31	4.14	

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8.	M	40-60	53.5	21.8	24.6	SCL	1.32	4.09	16.2	
		0-20	62.3	22.3	15.4	SL	1.30	3.72		
		20-40	60.4	23.4	16.2	SL	1.32	3.20		
	C	40-60	58.4	24.6	17.0	SL	1.34	2.80		16.8
		0-20	62.8	22.0	15.2	SL	1.30	3.74		
		20-40	60.7	23.1	16.2	SL	1.31	3.37		
9.	M	40-60	58.0	25.1	16.9	SL	1.32	3.22	9.6	
		0-20	45.5	36.5	18.0	L	1.29	6.84		
		20-40	43.6	36.8	19.6	L	1.30	5.83		
	C	40-60	42.7	35.9	21.4	L	1.31	4.85	9.9	
		0-20	44.2	37.3	18.5	L	1.29	6.84		
		20-40	43.0	36.2	20.3	L	1.29	5.83		
10.	M	40-60	42.7	36.4	20.9	L	1.29	5.11	4.7	
		0-20	59.5	19.6	20.9	SCL	1.30	4.35		
		20-40	58.4	19.8	21.8	SCL	1.31	3.54		
	C	40-60	57.6	19.5	22.9	SCL	1.32	3.22	4.9	
		0-20	59.2	19.9	20.9	SCL	1.30	4.36		
		20-40	58.6	19.7	21.7	SCL	1.30	4.01		
11.	M	40-60	57.6	19.4	23.0	SCL	1.31	3.97	7.3	
		0-20	25.5	59.7	14.8	SiL	1.28	11.83		
		20-40	24.7	59.5	15.8	SiL	1.29	10.93		
	C	40-60	24.1	59.0	16.9	SiL	1.31	9.73	7.6	
		0-20	25.7	59.4	14.9	SiL	1.28	11.97		
		20-40	24.8	59.5	15.7	SiL	1.28	11.77		
12.	M	40-60	24.2	59.0	16.8	SiL	1.29	10.83	9.5	
		0-20	47.5	33.1	19.4	L	1.28	5.78		
		20-40	45.3	34.6	20.1	L	1.29	4.77		
	C	40-60	44.2	34.4	21.4	L	1.31	4.12	9.8	
		0-20	47.7	33.0	19.3	L	1.28	5.73		
		20-40	45.6	34.2	20.2	L	1.29	5.34		
13.	M	40-60	44.4	34.3	21.3	L	1.30	4.81	4.6	
		0-20	62.4	14.7	22.9	SCL	1.29	3.19		
		20-40	60.7	15.5	23.8	SCL	1.30	2.62		
	C	40-60	58.7	15.6	25.7	SCL	1.31	2.12	4.8	
		0-20	61.3	15.1	23.6	SCL	1.29	3.39		
		20-40	60.8	15.6	23.6	SCL	1.29	3.17		
14.	M	40-60	58.6	15.5	25.9	SCL	1.30	2.57	4.2	
		0-20	60.5	10.6	28.9	SCL	1.26	1.89		
		20-40	58.6	11.7	29.7	SCL	1.27	1.73		
	C	40-60	56.2	12.3	31.5	SCL	1.28	1.48	4.4	
		0-20	60.4	10.7	28.9	SCL	1.26	1.90		
		20-40	58.4	12.2	29.4	SCL	1.26	1.80		
15.	M	40-60	56.4	12.2	31.4	SCL	1.27	1.68	3.2	
		0-20	33.2	36.2	30.6	CL	1.21	2.48		
		20-40	31.5	37.0	31.5	CL	1.22	2.38		
	C	40-60	30.1	36.7	33.2	CL	1.23	2.10	3.3	
		0-20	33.1	36.7	30.2	CL	1.20	2.51		
		20-40	31.4	37.0	31.6	CL	1.21	2.43		
16.	M	40-60	30.4	36.3	33.3	CL	1.22	2.33	1.1	
		0-20	50.5	9.3	40.2	SC	1.21	0.99		
		20-40	47.6	11.6	40.8	SC	1.22	0.92		
	C	40-60	44.2	13.6	42.2	SC	1.23	0.79	1.2	
		0-20	50.4	9.6	40.0	SC	1.20	1.00		
		20-40	47.4	11.6	41.0	SC	1.21	0.98		
17.	M	40-60	44.2	13.7	42.1	SC	1.22	0.86	4.3	
		0-20	55.4	23.2	21.4	SCL	1.29	4.26		
		20-40	52.7	25.4	21.9	SCL	1.30	3.55		
	C	40-60	51.2	25.4	23.4	SCL	1.31	3.12	4.5	
		0-20	55.3	23.5	21.2	SCL	1.29	4.36		
		20-40	52.6	25.4	22.0	SCL	1.29	4.12		
		40-60	51.1	25.4	23.5	SCL	1.30	4.09		

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18.	M	0-20	62.4	13.8	23.8	SCL	1.28	3.01	4.2
		20-40	60.4	15.1	24.5	SCL	1.29	2.47	
		40-60	57.6	16.1	26.3	SCL	1.30	2.06	
	C	0-20	62.3	14.1	23.6	SCL	1.28	3.15	4.4
		20-40	60.0	15.8	24.2	SCL	1.28	3.06	
		40-60	57.8	15.8	26.4	SCL	1.29	2.91	
19.	M	0-20	23.4	59.8	16.8	SiL	1.26	9.90	8.1
		20-40	22.4	60.0	17.6	SiL	1.27	9.27	
		40-60	20.9	59.9	19.2	SiL	1.28	8.07	
	C	0-20	23.6	59.6	16.8	SiL	1.26	9.92	8.4
		20-40	22.2	60.3	17.5	SiL	1.26	9.76	
		40-60	20.7	60.0	19.3	SiL	1.27	9.39	
20.	M	0-20	64.8	20.8	14.4	SL	1.35	9.62	14.6
		20-40	62.1	22.6	15.3	SL	1.36	8.59	
		40-60	60.4	22.2	17.4	SL	1.37	7.24	
	C	0-20	64.8	20.8	14.4	SL	1.34	9.62	15.2
		20-40	62.0	22.7	15.3	SL	1.35	9.17	
		40-60	60.2	22.3	17.5	SL	1.36	8.60	
21.	M	0-20	69.8	13.8	16.4	SL	1.35	7.24	13.6
		20-40	67.4	15.1	17.5	SL	1.36	6.74	
		40-60	65.1	15.8	19.1	SL	1.37	5.14	
	C	0-20	69.4	14.1	16.5	SL	1.34	8.71	14.1
		20-40	67.2	15.4	17.4	SL	1.35	7.15	
		40-60	65.0	15.8	19.2	SL	1.36	6.39	
22.	M	0-20	64.4	6.4	29.2	SCL	1.28	7.74	4.5
		20-40	62.4	7.7	29.9	SCL	1.29	6.49	
		40-60	60.7	7.1	32.2	SCL	1.30	5.86	
	C	0-20	64.3	6.7	29.0	SCL	1.27	7.98	4.7
		20-40	62.3	7.9	29.8	SCL	1.28	7.13	
		40-60	60.7	7.3	32.0	SCL	1.29	6.74	
23.	M	0-20	54.3	17.3	28.4	SCL	1.26	2.09	4.6
		20-40	52.4	18.5	29.1	SCL	1.27	1.86	
		40-60	51.5	18.1	30.4	SCL	1.28	1.56	
	C	0-20	54.4	17.0	28.6	SCL	1.25	2.13	4.8
		20-40	52.2	18.5	29.3	SCL	1.26	2.02	
		40-60	51.4	18.3	30.3	SCL	1.27	1.88	
24.	M	0-20	42.5	37.2	20.3	L	1.27	5.46	10.2
		20-40	40.2	38.4	21.4	L	1.28	4.62	
		40-60	38.7	37.6	23.7	L	1.29	3.96	
	C	0-20	42.2	37.6	20.2	L	1.26	5.54	10.5
		20-40	40.3	38.4	21.3	L	1.27	5.04	
		40-60	38.8	37.3	23.9	L	1.28	4.58	
25.	M	0-20	32.4	46.3	21.3	SiL	1.26	5.58	7.3
		20-40	30.2	47.6	22.2	SiL	1.27	5.05	
		40-60	28.3	47.6	24.1	SiL	1.28	4.53	
	C	0-20	32.7	46.1	21.2	SiL	1.25	5.61	7.6
		20-40	30.4	47.3	22.3	SiL	1.25	5.26	
		40-60	28.2	47.6	24.2	SiL	1.26	4.98	
26.	M	0-20	58.3	19.3	22.4	SCL	1.30	3.71	4.6
		20-40	56.2	20.6	23.2	SCL	1.31	3.25	
		40-60	53.7	20.7	25.6	SCL	1.32	2.98	
	C	0-20	58.4	19.2	22.4	SCL	1.29	3.72	4.8
		20-40	56.3	20.4	23.3	SCL	1.30	3.43	
		40-60	53.7	20.8	25.5	SCL	1.31	3.12	
27.	M	0-20	62.5	16.0	21.5	SCL	1.31	3.97	4.7
		20-40	61.5	16.3	22.2	SCL	1.32	3.62	
		40-60	60.2	15.6	24.2	SCL	1.33	3.01	
	C	0-20	62.4	16.1	21.5	SCL	1.30	4.18	4.9
		20-40	61.4	16.2	22.4	SCL	1.30	4.02	
		40-60	60.2	15.5	24.3	SCL	1.31	3.85	
28.		0-20	59.6	29.9	10.5	SL	1.39	16.27	

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	M	20-40	57.4	31.2	11.4	SL	1.40	14.41	12.6
		40-60	55.7	31.4	12.9	SL	1.41	11.87	
	C	0-20	59.7	29.7	10.6	SL	1.38	16.49	13.1
		20-40	57.6	30.9	11.5	SL	1.39	14.61	
		40-60	55.6	31.4	13.0	SL	1.40	12.02	
	29.	M	0-20	64.3	8.2	27.5	SCL	1.28	2.03
20-40			63.7	8.1	28.2	SCL	1.29	1.78	
40-60			60.7	9.2	30.1	SCL	1.30	1.52	
C		0-20	64.2	8.1	27.7	SCL	1.27	2.07	4.5
		20-40	63.6	8.2	28.2	SCL	1.27	1.95	
		40-60	60.7	9.0	30.3	SCL	1.28	1.70	
30.	M	0-20	58.7	18.8	22.5	SCL	1.30	3.66	4.4
		20-40	57.4	19.7	22.9	SCL	1.31	3.38	
		40-60	56.3	19.5	24.2	SCL	1.32	3.00	
	C	0-20	58.5	19.1	22.4	SCL	1.29	3.71	4.6
		20-40	57.3	19.8	22.9	SCL	1.30	3.55	
		40-60	56.4	19.2	24.4	SCL	1.31	3.13	

M- Sugarcane mechanized soil, C-Control- Non mechanized soil

Soil compaction in sugarcane field induced by mechanisation

The soil samples were collected are analyzed (Hesse, P.R., 1971) for the determination of soil physical properties. It was inferred that, though the sugarcane is being cultivated in a wide range of soil textures from loamy sand to clay loam, it prefers the soils registered with light (sandy) texture with good hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate as well as optimum bulk density. The effect of mechanization was well pronounced in soil physical parameters like bulk density, hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate which resulted with slightly higher values compared to non mechanized soils, wherein, slightly higher values were recorded at lower depths (20 – 40 cm) and (40 – 60 cm) than the surface soil (0 – 20 cm) (Hakanson, 2005). This might be due to small textural differences in the soils chosen in this study. Similar results are also reported by Naseri *et al.*, 2007.

The soil bulk density varied from 1.20 to 1.41 Mg m⁻³. As expected, the mechanised fields had more values for soil bulk density (Hetz, 2001). The highest value of 1.41 Mg m⁻³ was found in a mechanised sugarcane field, while the lowest value recorded in a manual labour harvested sugarcane field with 1.20 Mg m⁻³. This evidenced from increased bulk density and decreased hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate in all the 30 locations. This results were in conformity with studies performed on the effect of machines traffic in sugarcane fields, which increases soil compaction directly on tires paths and in some cases in regions near the tracks formed by machine tires (Horn *et al.*, 2001). Clay soils are most susceptible to compaction because their fine particles hold that more water for a longer period than the sand or loam soil. Clay soils remain in a plastic state, most of the year, which make them compactable when harvesting with machine and traffic load is applied. Similar results were also reported by Naseri *et al.*, 2007. Harvester and tractor tire sliding also has strong influence on the increase of soil compaction (Otto *et al.*, 2011). The maximum percentage of pores with diameters of 20-50 µm in the 40-60 cm depth layer in sugarcane seedbed areas occurred because the wheel track width of the harvesting machines was not adjusted to the sugarcane spacing, which caused soil compaction in the region of root proliferating areas and the findings are in accordance to the field investigations by Braunack and McGarry (2006).

Experiment-II

Management of soil compaction

The impact of mechanisation on soil physical characteristics has to be ascertained and through which appropriate agro-technologies could be formulated to safeguard the soil properties, fertility and its productivity. The plant crop was raised during 2017-18 in the early season and after harvest of the plant crop, the sprouted sugarcane was allowed to grow for ratoon study during 2018-19 to find out the subsequent impact of mechanised cane cultivation and harvest on soil compaction. The data on varied soil physico-chemical

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characteristics of soil profile at different depth, sugarcane biometrics, yield and quality parameters are documented.

Growth parameters of sugarcane

The result on germination percentage reveals that chisel ploughing significantly recorded highest percentage (89.2) compared to two disc ploughing and farmers practice. In addition, the tillage operations with chisel plough combined with application of FYM significantly registered highest germination percentage (93.6) followed by coir pith and green manure (**Calma, 1933**). In ratoon crop also the results revealed that chisel ploughing significantly recorded highest sprouting of 2,74,200/ha compared to two disc ploughing and farmers practice. Further, the tillage operations with chisel plough combined with application of FYM significantly registered highest sprouting of 2,87,800/ha, followed by coir pith and green manure applications. In plant crop, the result indicated that, among the tillage practices the maximum tiller population was recorded in chisel ploughing (2,42,000/ha) and it was on par with double disc ploughing (2,36,520/ha). Among the soil amendments, application of farm yard manure @ 12.5 t/ha recorded the maximum tillers of 2,48,370 per hectare. In ratoon crop, the maximum tiller population was recorded with chisel ploughing with 1,40,400/ha and it was on par with double disc plough (1,38,200/ha). Among the soil amendments, application of farm yard manure @ 12.5 t/ha recorded the maximum tillers of 1,46,700 per hectare. The increased values of germination, sprouting and tiller population were due to the effect of deep subsoil ploughing with chisel plough in breaking the soil hard pan and the farm yard manure application that improves soil structure and with resulted better seed bed, improve nutrient exchange, effective utilization of nutrients and increase growth and growth attributes (**Garside et al., 2009**).

Root growth and establishment of sugarcane

In plant crop, the maximum root dry weight of 126.4 g/plant was recorded under chisel ploughing and it was comparable with double disc plough with 124.6 g/plant. Among the subplot treatments, FYM application @ 12.5 t/ha recorded the maximum root dry weight of 131.5 g/plant and it was followed by composted coir pith @ 10.0 t/ha, green manure *in-situ* @ 40 t/ha and press mud @ 25 t/ha, which recorded 128.8, 126.3 and 125.1 g/plant of root dry weight respectively on 120 DAP. The adoption of both ploughing and organic matter application in sugarcane farming imparts specific effects in improvement of soil physical conditions resulting in better root development and higher sugarcane yield. These results are in accordance with the findings of **Esteban et al., (2019)**. In ratoon crop, root dry weight was significantly maximum with 123.3 g/plant with chisel ploughing and it was followed by double disc plough, which recorded 116.2 g/plant. After harvest, the treatment showed lower soil penetration resistance in planting row up to the depth of 0- 30 cm. The higher soil penetration resistance on sub surface layers of the soil may indicate the effect of previous crop management effect. Another factor which might have influenced penetration resistance in the innermost profile layers is the effect of pressure by the upper layers on the deepest layers as illustrated by **Gao et al., 2016**. Among the subplot treatments, FYM application @ 12.5 t/ha recorded the maximum root dry weight of 123.9 g/plant and it was followed by composted coir pith @ 10.0 t/ha, green manure *in-situ* @ 40 t/ha and press mud @ 25 t/ha, which recorded 121.3, 119.0 and 117.8 g/plant root dry weight respectively on 120 DAP. The increase in root dry weight on 120 DAP due to the incorporation of farm yard manure with chisel ploughing are due to the effect of the improved environment in the soil, encouraging proliferation of roots and resulted into more absorption of water and nutrients from the soil (**Otto et al., 2011**).

Root dry weight at harvest of sugarcane plant crop under chisel ploughing recorded the maximum root dry weight of 136.3 g/plant and followed by double disc plough, which registered 133.2 g/plant. In subplot treatments FYM @ 12.5 t recorded the maximum of 142.1 g/plant of root dry weight (**Ng Cheong et al., 1999**). In ratoon crop, the chisel ploughing recorded the maximum root dry weight of 134.6 g/plant followed by double disc ploughing (125.4 g/plant). Regarding the subplot treatments the FYM @ 12.5 t incorporation recorded the maximum of 132.6 g/plant of root dry weight at harvest (**Eseban et al., 2019**). It might be due to combination of chisel ploughing and organic manures application which increases the root growth thereby increasing the uptake and better utilization of macro and micro-nutrients. Higher root weight is also obtained due to entry of water

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into plant roots and sustained nutrient supply, through development of improved micro-environmental conditions, especially the activities of soil microorganisms involved in nutrient transformation, fixation and participation in carbon assimilation, photosynthesis, starch formation, translocation of protein and sugar (**Gao et al., 2016**).

Yield parameter and yield of sugarcane

The chisel ploughing significantly recorded the maximum millable canes (1,42,650/ha), individual cane weight (1.73 kg), cane length (329.6 cm), cane girth (3.15 cm), number of internodes (24.8/cane), length of internode (12.26 cm) and cane yield (141.6 t/ha) and it was followed by double disc ploughing, which recorded millable canes (1,38,250/ha), individual cane weight (1.69 kg), cane length (322.5 cm), cane girth (3.15 cm), number of internodes (23.7/cane), length of internode (12.14) and cane yield (137.6 t/ha) in plant crops reported by **Hornet et al., 2009** and **Ismael et al., 2007**. In ratoon crop, the chisel ploughing significantly recorded the maximum millable canes (1,37,580/ha), individual cane weight (2.42 kg), cane length (331.24 cm), cane girth (3.3 cm), number of internodes (27.0/cane), length of internode (12.0 cm) and cane yield (136.3 t/ha) and it was followed by double disc ploughing, which recorded millable cane (1,25,630/ha), individual cane weight (2.23 kg), cane length (315.45 cm), cane girth (3.13 cm), number of internodes (24.6/cane), length of internode (11.5) and cane yield (123.4 t/ha). The combined application of chisel ploughing and farm yard manure provides more amount of nutrients through steady supply which encourages better cell expansion, root development and influence the higher yield attributes. Similar findings were also reported by **Garside et al., 2016**.

In the sub plot, application of FYM @ 12.5 t/ha recorded significantly the maximum millable canes (1,43,560/ha), individual cane weight (1.72 kg), cane length (340.3 cm), cane girth (3.19 cm), number of internodes (24.3/cane), internode length (12.73 cm) and cane yield (140.9 t/ha) and it was comparable with composted coir pith @ 10.0 t/ha, green manure *in-situ* @ 40 t/ha and press mud @ 25 t/ha treatments, which recorded millable canes (1,40,590/ha, 1,37,890/ha and 1,36,540/ha), individual cane weight (1.70 kg, 1.65 kg and 1.64 kg), cane length (336.4 cm, 325.8 cm and 324.2 cm), cane girth (3.16 cm, 3.06 cm and 3.04 cm), number of internodes (24.0/cane, 23.2/cane and 23.1/cane), internode length (12.58 cm, 12.18 cm and 12.12 cm) and cane yield (139.3 t/ha, 134.9 t/ha and 134.2 t/ha) respectively (**Sousa et al., 2017**). The organic manures have multiple benefits due to the balanced supply of nutrients (**Jayachandran et al., 2004**), especially farm yard manure has been known to improve soil fertility through increasing the soil organic matter, available nitrogen, concentration of nutrients near the soil surface in available form and reduces the nutrient losses through leaching and soil erosion (**Ng Cheong et al., 2008**).

Among the sub plot treatments, in ratoon cane the application of FYM @ 12.5 t/ha recorded significantly the maximum millable canes (1,33,880/ha), individual cane weight (2.37 kg), cane length (327.1 cm), cane girth (3.29 cm), number of internodes (26.0/cane), internode length (12.0 cm) and cane yield (130.6 t/ha) and it was comparable with composted coir pith @ 10.0 t/ha, green manure *in-situ* @ 40 t/ha and press mud @ 25 t/ha treatments, which recorded millable canes (1,31,110/ha, 1,28,580/ha and 1,27,320/ha), individual cane weight (2.35 kg, 2.27 kg and 2.26 kg), cane length (323.3 cm, 313.1 cm and 311.5 cm), cane girth (3.26 cm, 3.15 cm and 3.14 cm), number of internodes (25.7/cane, 24.9/cane and 24.8/cane), internode length (11.9 cm, 11.5 cm and 11.5 cm) and cane yield (129.1 t/ha, 125.1 t/ha and 124.4 t/ha) respectively (**Kirchmann and Witter., 1992**). The incorporation of farm yard manure releases organic substances *viz.*, organic acid, amino acids, sugars, vitamins and mucilage during crop growth as well as after decomposition (**Levi-Minziet al., 1986**). These substances are capable to bind soil particles together and form better soil aggregation. **Mohamed Ammanullah (2007)** found that the incorporation of farm yard manure @ 12 t ha⁻¹ decreased the bulk density by 8.1 per cent at 0-15 cm and 2.3 per cent at 15-30 cm depth over control.

Quality parameter and sugar yield of sugarcane

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In plant crop the maximum brix (20.76 %), pole (18.21 %), purity (87.72%), CCS (12.55 %) and sugar yield (17.77 t/ha) were significantly recorded with the M₁ chisel plough and followed double disc plough, which recorded brix (20.62 %), pole (18.11 %), purity (87.83%), CCS (12.54 %) and sugar yield (17.25 t/ha).

In ratoon crop also a significant results were recorded with the maximum brix (23.56 %), pole (18.89 %), purity (80.18 %), CCS (12.43 %) and sugar yield (16.93 t/ha) under M₁ chisel plough and followed double disc plough, with the brix (22.42 %), pole (17.24 %), purity (76.9 %), CCS (12.54 %) and sugar yield (15.48 t/ha). It was due to the judicious use of organic manures and chisel ploughing. On efficient land preparation to obtain good soil with facilitating profuse root growth and its proliferation to deeper soil layer to absorb the available nutrients at its maximum for effective synthesis of sugars and its subsequent storage, which enabled sugarcane plant to assimilate sufficient photosynthesis resulting in increased sucrose accumulation in the sugarcane stem, it was evidenced earlier by **Ng Chaeong et al., (1999)**

Among the sub plot treatments in plant crop the application of FYM @ 12.5 t/ha recorded significantly the maximum brix (20.78 %), pole (18.22 %), purity (92.29 %), CCS (12.55 %) and sugar yield (17.68 t/ha) and it was comparable with composted coir pith @ 10.0 t/ha, green manure *in-situ* @ 40 t/ha and press mud @ 25 t/ha, which recorded brix (20.75 %, 20.81 % and 20.71%), pole (18.20 %, 18.23 % and 18.16 %), purity (91.23 %, 88.36 % and 87.91 %), CCS (12.54 %, 12.56 % and 12.52 %) and sugar yield (17.47 t/ha, 16.94 t/ha and 16.80 t/ha) respectively.

A similar type of results were also been resulted in ratoon crop with application of FYM @ 12.5 t/ha which have recorded significantly the maximum brix (22.93 %), pole (17.96 %), purity (82.43 %), CCS (11.66 %) and sugar yield (15.28 t/ha) and it was comparable with composted coir pith @ 10.0 t/ha, green manure *in-situ* @ 40 t/ha and press mud @ 25 t/ha, which recorded brix (22.89 %, 22.96 % and 22.84 %), pole (17.94 %, 17.97 % and 17.94 %), purity (81.49 %, 78.92 % and 78.52 %), CCS (11.65 %, 11.66 % and 11.63 %) and sugar yield (15.09 t/ha, 14.63 t/ha and 14.52 t/ha) respectively as it was evidenced earlier by **Ng Chaeong et al., (2008)**. This is due to synergistic effect of chisel ploughing and organic manure, as well as the slow release of nutrients throughout the crop growth, to synthesis more photosynthates and translocating the same from source to sink. The release of N along with improved soil physical properties, thus enhanced the crop growth and quality attributes of sugarcane (**Levi-Minzi et al., 1986**).

Regarding the cost benefit ratio, the chisel plough recorded the maximum of 2.83 and among the amendments, the farm yard manure 12.5 @ t/ha recorded 2.87 in plant crop. The same trend was also noticed in ratoon crop with the chisel plough (3.46) and among the amendments, the farm yard manure @ 12.5 t/ha was recorded 3.04. The application of amendment such as farmyard manure with chisel ploughing recorded the maximum B:C ratio of 4.22.

Soil physical properties on soil compaction

Bulk density

Tillage operations do not affect texture, but they do alter structure (soil particle aggregation). Primary tillage operations, such as ploughing, generally decrease bulk density and increase pore space, which is beneficial. Secondary tillage operation generally increases bulk density and decreases pore space (**Gae et al., 2016**). The soil compaction resulting from cultivation can be detrimental to plant growth. The movement of machinery over the field forces solid particles into spaces once occupied by water or air, resulting in less pore space and increased bulk density (**Yang, 1974**). Hence any management practice that influences the soil structure and organic matter status of soil would naturally influence the bulk density. In plant crop among the tillage methods chisel ploughing registered its efficiency of breaking the compaction, thereby decreased the bulk density of post harvest soil of sugarcane at all the depths *viz.*, 0 -15, 15 – 30 and 30 – 45 cm and it is on par with double disc plough twice. Comparing the different sources of organics, FYM application @ 12.5 t ha⁻¹

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recorded significantly lesser bulk density and it is at par with press mud @ 25 t ha⁻¹, composted coir pith @ 10 t ha⁻¹ and greenmanure in situ @ 40 t ha⁻¹ at all the depths. Similar type of influence both the tillage operations and application of different sources of organics reduced the bulk density of the post harvest soil of sugarcane at 0 – 15 cm depth (Gaeet *et al.*, 2016).

Accordingly, chisel plough along with farm yard manure application registered its superiority in reducing the bulk density compared to other treatments. This could be due to organics have a bulk density much lower than that of mineral soils and therefore, the application of organics can reduce the overall bulk density of the soil, further farm yard manure is very porous nature which improve soil aeration thus reduced the bulk density (Yang, 1974). Thus, mixing of organics with a mineral soil reduces the bulk density of the soil even at lower depth, which is indication of breakage of compaction (Levi-Minzi *et al.*, 1986).

In ratoon crop a similar trend of the main crop results were observed revealing the persistence of treatments effect. Significantly lower bulk density was observed in chisel plough with FYM @ 12.5 t ha⁻¹ applied treatment. Hence any management practice that influences the soil structure and organic matter status of soil would naturally influence the bulk density. Incorporation of farm yard manure also had a significant effect on bulk density which has endorsed by higher rate of N mineralization as a result of high cation exchange capacity, slow and steady release of N that make the soil more productive (Yang, 1974).

Particle density

Particle density varies with the type of soil minerals present as well as the amount of organic matter. Texture and structure do not affect particle density. However, organic matter, which is a soil solid, readily influences particle density. Soils high in organic matter have lower particle densities than soils similar in texture that are low in organic matter. Soil particle density generally increases with soil depth because of the concurrent decrease in organic matter (Yang, 1974).

Among the tillage practices, there is no significant change in the particle density of post harvest soil of sugarcane at shallow depth viz., 0 – 15 in plant crop. However, there is a significant different found at lower depths and lower value was registered in farmers practice (16" single disc). Similar results were observed by Yang (1974). The concentration of compressing forces applied on the ground with machinery traffic in the inter rows reduced soil compaction in the ratooned areas of plant growth and resulted in lower particle density and higher porosity in planting row. Both different tillage practices and application of different sources of organics reduced the particle density of the post harvest soil of sugarcane at 0 – 15 cm depth. However, chisel plough along with farm yard manure application registered its superiority in reducing the particle density compared to other treatments even at lower depths, which was at par with double disc plough twice coupled with farm yard manure application (Levi-Minzi *et al.*, 1986).

The influence of treatments effect on particle density was seen in the first ratoon itself. There was a similar trend as that of main crop was observed viz., chisel plough along with farm yard manure application registered its superiority in reducing the particle density compared to other treatments even at lower depths, which was at par with double disc plough twice coupled with farm yard manure application. However, incorporation of sugarcane trash to the residual crop had further decreased the particle density in all the treatments evenly at surface soil viz., 0 – 15 cm compared to subsurface soils.

This was mainly due to the combined application of chisel ploughing and farm yard manure application for plant crop and trash incorporation in ratoon crop results in improved soil conditions which encourages higher proliferation of roots and results in more absorption of water and nutrients from the soil. These results also get supported by Ismael *et al.*, (2007).

Porosity

Pore space of soil, among other parameters is influenced to a greater extent by the amount of clay and organic matter content. In the present study, since the soil of the experimental site was clay and further addition of manures as source of organic carbon the positive influence of clay and organic carbon results in higher

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porosity value with the organics treatments. Further, the increase in porosity might be due to the porous nature of organics and its concomitant changes in soil aggregation and improved aeration due to tillage which increases macro porosity and improved supply of oxygen to the soil even at lower depths. The results obtained by **Esteban *et al.*, (2019)** also indicated constraints in sugarcane root development and implies to reduce stronger potential of root to absorb nutrients and water from the soil. However, the extent of changes will depend on the porosity characteristics of different organic sources and application rates. As bulk density and porosity are indirectly related, improvement in porosity or particle density would have reduced the bulk density, thereby improving the soil properties in both plant and ratoon crop.

Root penetration

Penetrometer resistance is often used as an indicator of the resistance of soil to root elongation. Root-restricting soil layers, with high mechanical impedance, can thus be identified with a penetrometer reading. Generally, a cone index value of 300 psi or greater is indicative of compaction. Root growth decreases linearly with increasing penetration resistance, until practically stopping above 300 psi. In the present study, chisel and double disc plough are good for soil preparation in loosening of the soil even at deeper depth *viz.*, 30-45cm. The Farmers practice (16" Single disc) yielded only slightly less favourable soil strengths than chisel and double disc plough at deeper layers. The shallow ploughing was totally ineffective in creating a favourable root environment. Results obtained with the penetrometer were confirmed by bulk density values, which are lower for the Chisel and double disc ploughing.

In the residual study also, similar trend in reduction of soil bulk density is registered for increase in porosity. Soil compaction is a serious issue that affects the growth of crop roots (**Otto *et al.*, 2011**). Penetrometer resistance (or cone index) is often used as an indicator of the resistance of soil to root elongation, and is expressed as the ratio between the force required to push a metal cone into a soil versus the basal area of the cone. Root-restricting soil layers, with high mechanical impedance, can thus be identified with a penetrometer reading (**Esteban *et al.*, (2019)**). Generally, a cone index value of 300 psi or greater is indicative of compaction. Root growth decreases linearly with increasing penetration resistance, until practically stopping above 300 psi. In the present study, similar trend in bulk density was also recorded in penetrometer reading.

Hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate

The hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate are generally low in sandy loam and clay soils due to the presence of excess clay leads to the clogging of soil pores which is responsible for water logging condition. The value of increased porosity in terms of water retention and movement need not be over emphasized. The marked effect of tillage and organic additions in increasing the hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate could also be observed in the present study. The promising effect of organics in improving the hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate of clay soil indicated that, organics has a very porous nature and improved physical condition; its application to soil improves soil aeration. Improved aeration will be partly due to increases in macro porosity with resulting higher air-filled porosity and improved supply of oxygen to soil under a wide range of soil water conditions (**Ng Cheong *et al.*, 2008**). With positive effect on bulk density, porosity particularly macrospores supplemented by better water stable aggregates due to the application of organics and tillage enhanced the water transmission characteristics considerably. The ability of the soil to hold more moisture and at the same time facilitate better water movement is a matter of betterment in soil-water-plant relationships in both plant and ratoon crop.

Conclusions

Sugarcane was cultivated in a wide range of soil textures from loamy sand to clay loam (loamy sand, sandy loam, loam, silt loam, sandy clay loam and clay loam) soils in Cuddalore and Villupuram districts of

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Tamil Nadu State. Most of the non-mechanized field soils registered with good hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate as well as optimum bulk density. There was a mechanization induced soil compaction development in all the textural soils compared to non-mechanized field soils. This was evidenced from poor soil physical condition induced by mechanization viz., increased bulk density and decreased hydraulic conductivity and infiltration rate. The effect was well pronounced at lower depths viz., (20 – 40 cm) and (40 – 60 cm) than the surface soil (0 – 20 cm).

Among the methods of tillage, chisel plough registered its efficiency of breaking the compaction, thereby decreased the bulk density, particle density and penetrometer resistance and increased the porosity, HC and IR of post-harvest soil of sugarcane at all the depths viz., 0 -15, 15 – 30 and 30 – 45 cm. As a result maximum cane yield of 141.6 t/ha, sugar yield of 17.77 t/ha and CCS of 12.55 % in plant crop were registered. The same treatment recorded the maximum cane yield of 136.3 t/ha, sugar yield of 16.94 t/ha and CCS of 12.43 % in ratoon crop

Comparing the different sources of organics, FYM application @ 12.5 t ha⁻¹ recorded significantly lesser bulk density, particle density and penetrometer resistance and higher the porosity, HC and IR at all the depths. As a result the maximum cane yield of 140.9 t/ha, sugar yield of 17.68 and CCS of 12.55 % in plant crop and the same treatment recorded the maximum cane yield of 136.3 t/ha, sugar yield of 15.28 and CCS of 1.66 % in ratoon crop.

Both different tillage practices and application of different sources of organics reduced the bulk density, particle density and penetrometer resistance and increased the porosity, HC and IR of the post harvest soil of sugarcane at 0 – 15 cm depth. However, chisel plough along with Farm Yard Manure application registered its superiority in reducing the bulk density, particle density and penetrometer resistance and increasing the porosity, HC and IR compared to other treatments. As a result the highest values of growth and yield parameters and cane yield (143.3 t/ha), sugar yield of 17.88 t/ha and CCS of 12.47 % and B:C ratio of 4.22 in plant crop was observed. The same treatment combination recorded the best growth and yield parameters and cane yield (143.3 t/ha), sugar yield of 17.88 t/ha and CCS of 12.47 %. The same treatment combination recorded the B:C ratio of 4.22 in ratoon crop.

References

- i *Braunack, M., V. and McGarry, D., 2006. Traffic control and tillage strategies for harvesting and planting of sugarcane (Saccharum officinarum) in Australia. Soil Tillage Res. 89: 86-102.*
- ii *Calma, V. C., 1933. Studies on germination degree of tillering and vigour of top and cut-back seed pieces of POJ-78 sugarcane (Saccharum officinarum), Phillipine Agriculturist, Laguna., 21: P.585-612.*
- iii *Esteban, D. A. A., Z. M. De Souza, C. A. Tormena, L. H. Lovera, E. D. Lima, I. N. De Oliveira and N. D. Ribiero. 2019. Soil compaction, root system and productivity of sugarcane under different row spacing and controlled traffic at harvest. Soil Tillage Res., 187: pp. 60-71.*
- iv *Gao, W., W. R. Whalley, Z. Tran, J. Liu and T. Ren. 2016. A single model to predict soil Penetrometer resistance as a function of density, drying and depth in the field. Soil Tillage Res., 155: pp. 90-198.*
- v *Garside, A. L., M. J. Bell and B. G. Robetham, 2009. Row spacing and planting density effects on the growth and yield of sugarcane. 2. Strategies for the adoption of controlled traffic. Crop Pasture Sci., 60: pp. 544-554.*
- vi *Glyn James. (2004) Sugarcane, Second edition, Blackwell Science Ltd., 9600 Garsington road, Oxford OX4 2DQ, UK.*

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- vii *Hakansson, I., 2005. Machinery-induced compaction of arable soils. Incidence-consequences-counter-measures. Reports from the Division of Soil Management No.109, Department of Soil Science, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala.*
- viii *Hesse, P.R., 1971. A Text book of soil Chemical Analysis, John Murry, London.*
- ix *Hetz., E.J., 2001. Soil compaction potential of tractors and other heavy agricultural machines used in Chile. Agricultural Mechanization in Asia, Africa and Latin America, vol. 32: pp. 38-42*
- x *Horn, R., T. Way, J. Rostek., 2001. Effect of repeated wheeling on stress/strain properties and ecological consequences in structured arable soils. Revista de la CienciadelSuelo y Nutricion Vegetal, 1: pp. 34-40.*
- xi *Ismael F.M., S Seeruttun, C. Barbe, A. Gaungoo, 2007. Improving cane productivity with dual row planting in Maritius. Proc.Int.Soc.Sugarcane Technol. 26 (2007), pp. 220-226.*
- xii *Jackson, M. L. 1973. Soil chemical analysis. Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India.*
- xiii *Jayachandran, M., G.sudhakar and S.Giridharan, 2004. Effect of organic mulches on the weed control efficiency in sugarcane, Madras Agric. J.91.91 (1-3): 150-152.*
- xiv *Kirchmann, H. and e.Witter., 1992. Composition of fresh, aerobic and anaerobic manure decomposition. Plant Soil., 115: 35-41.*
- xv *Levi-Minzi, R., R.Riffaldi and A.Savizzi, 1986. Organic matter and nutrients in fresh and mature farm yard manure. Agric.Wastes., 16: 225-236.*
- xvi *Meade, G.P. And Chan, J.C.P. 1977. Cane sugar handbook 10th edition John Wiley and Sons. Inc.NewYark.*
- xvii *Mohamed Amanullah. M. 2007. Nutrient release pattern during composting poultry manure, research Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences, (3(4): 306-209.*
- xviii *Naseri, A.A., S.Jafari and M.Alimohammadi. 2007. Soil compaction due to sugarcane (Saccharumofficinarum) mechanical harvesting and the effect of subsoiling on the improvement of soil physical properties. J. of Applied Sci.7: 3639-3648.*
- xix *Ng Cheong, L.R., K.F.NgKeeKwang and C.C.DuPreez 2009. Soil compaction under sugarcane (Saccharumhybride sp.) cropping and mechanization in Mauritius. S.Afr.J.Plant Soil 26:4, 199-205.*
- xx *Ng Cheong, L.R., Riviere, V., Jacquin, E. and C. Soopramanien., 1999. Soil compaction due to mechanized harvesting and loading. Proc. Int. Soc. Sug. Cane Technol.23: 43-51.*
- xxi *Ng Cheong, L.R., K.F.NgKeeKwang and C.C.DuPreez 2008. Soil organic matter and microbial biomass as influenced by sugarcane (Saccharumhybride sp.) production practices in Mauritius. S.Afr.J.Plant Soil 25: 111-118.*
- xxii *Olsen, S. R., C. V. Cole, F. S. Waterable and L. A. Dean. 1954. Estimation of phosphorus in soils by extraction with sodium bicarbonate. United States Department of Agriculture. 939.*
- xxiii *Otto, R., A.P.silva, H.C.J.franco, E.C.A.Oliveira and P.c.o.Trivelin. 2011. High soil penetration resistance reduces sugarcane root system development. Soil Tillage Res.117.pp.201-210.*
- xxiv *Panse, V.G. and Sukhatme, P.V.1978. Statistical Methods for Agricultural Workers. ICAR, New Delhi.*
- xxv *Piper, C. S., 1966, Soil and Plant Analysis, Academic press, New York. 53-61.*
- xxvi *Sousa, G.S, Z.M.Sousa, Ris.Barboza and F.A.Silva. 2014. Effect of traffic control on the soil physical quality and the cultivation of sugarcane. Pesqui. Agropecu.Bras., 47: pp.603-612.*
- xxvii *Sousa, A.C.M, Z.M.Sousa, R.Poch Claret and J.l.R.Torres. 2017. Traffic control with autopilot as an alternative to decrease soil compaction in sugarcane areas. Trop.Subtrop.Aghroecosyst., 20: pp.173-181.*
- xxviii *Subbaiah, B.V. and Asija, G. L. 1956. A rapid procedure for the estimation of available nitrogen in soils. Curr. Sci., 65 (7): 477-480.*
- xxix *Walkley, A. and C.A.Black, 1934. An examination of the Degtiareff methods for determining soil organic matter and proposed modification of the chromic acid filtration methods. Soil sci., 37: 29-34.*

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- xxx *Wellington de Silva GuimaraesJunnyor, Etienne diserens, Isabella Clerici De Maria, Cezar Francisco Araujo Junior, Camila Viana Vieira Farhate, ZigomarMenezes de Souza 2019. Prediction of soil stress and compaction due to agricultural machines in sugarcane cultivation system with and without crop rotation, Science Direct, Science of the Total Environment, Vol 681 (1): 424-434.*
- xxxi *Yang,S.J.1974. Compaction studies on mechanized cane field soils. Influence of soil texture and moisture content on soil compaction. Taiwan Sug.Inst.Rep.64:11-22.*

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Table 5. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on growth parameters of sugarcane

Treatments	Tillers ('000/ha)				Root dry weight (g/plant) @120 DAP				Root dry weight (g/plant) @ Harvest				Millable cane ('000/ha)			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	257.00	250.23	237.89	248.37	134.2	132.3	128.0	131.5	144.7	141.5	140.1	149.1	151.49	146.82	132.38	143.56
S ₂	246.84	240.33	228.48	238.55	128.9	127.1	122.9	126.3	138.9	135.9	134.5	136.5	145.50	141.02	127.14	137.89
S ₃	244.42	237.98	226.24	236.21	127.6	125.8	121.8	125.1	137.6	134.6	133.2	135.1	144.08	139.63	125.90	136.54
S ₄	251.68	245.04	232.96	243.23	131.4	129.5	125.4	128.8	141.7	138.6	137.2	139.2	148.36	143.78	129.64	140.59
S ₅	210.06	204.52	194.43	203.00	109.7	108.1	104.6	107.5	118.3	115.7	114.5	116.1	123.82	120.00	108.20	117.34
Mean	242.00	235.62	224.00		126.4	124.6	120.5		136.3	133.2	131.9		142.65	138.25	120.65	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	1.68	2.31	3.84	7.92	0.89	1.23	2.03	4.19	0.96	1.32	2.20	4.53	0.97	1.34	2.22	4.58
CD(5%)	10.76	8.89	NS	NS	5.10	4.71	NS	NS	6.15	5.08	NS	NS	6.22	5.14	NS	NS

Table 6. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on yield parameters of sugarcane

Treatments	Individual cane weight (kg)				Cane length (cm)				Cane girth (cm)				No. of nodes / cane			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	1.82	1.78	1.56	1.72	346.7	339.2	335.0	340.3	3.31	3.31	2.96	3.19	26.1	24.9	21.8	24.3
S ₂	1.74	1.70	1.49	1.65	331.9	324.8	320.8	325.8	3.17	3.17	2.83	3.06	24.9	23.8	20.9	23.2
S ₃	1.73	1.69	1.48	1.64	330.3	323.1	319.1	324.2	3.16	3.16	2.82	3.04	24.9	23.7	20.8	23.1
S ₄	1.80	1.76	1.54	1.70	342.7	335.4	331.2	336.4	3.28	3.28	2.92	3.16	25.8	24.6	21.6	24.0
S ₅	1.55	1.52	1.33	1.47	296.2	289.8	286.2	290.7	2.83	2.83	2.53	2.73	22.3	21.3	18.6	20.7
Mean	1.73	1.69	1.48		329.6	322.5	318.5		3.15	3.15	2.81		24.8	23.7	20.7	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.012	0.016	0.027	0.055	2.33	3.20	5.31	10.95	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.10	0.17	0.23	0.38	0.78
CD (5%)	0.075	0.062	NS	NS	14.88	12.29	NS	NS	0.14	0.12	NS	NS	1.06	0.88	NS	NS

Table 7. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on yield parameters of sugarcane

Treatments	Internode length (cm)				Cane yield (t/ha)				Brix (%)				Pole (%)			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	12.90	12.77	12.51	12.73	148.9	144.7	128.9	140.9	20.91	20.73	20.72	20.78	18.20	18.20	18.15	18.22
S ₂	12.35	12.23	11.98	12.18	142.6	138.6	123.4	134.9	20.91	20.77	20.76	20.81	18.27	18.24	18.19	18.23
S ₃	12.29	12.17	11.91	12.12	141.9	137.9	122.8	134.2	20.80	20.66	20.65	20.71	18.25	18.15	18.10	18.16
S ₄	12.75	12.63	12.37	12.58	147.2	143.1	127.4	139.3	20.84	20.70	20.69	20.75	18.28	18.18	18.13	18.20
S ₅	11.02	10.91	10.69	10.87	127.2	123.6	110.1	120.3	20.33	20.24	20.23	20.27	17.95	17.77	17.73	17.82
Mean	12.26	12.14	11.89		141.6	137.6	122.5		20.76	20.62	20.61		18.21	18.11	18.06	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.09	0.12	0.20	0.41	0.96	1.32	2.30	4.48	0.15	0.20	0.34	0.70	0.13	0.18	0.30	0.61
CD (5%)	0.56	0.46	NS	NS	6.16	5.09	NS	NS	0.95	0.79	NS	NS	0.83	0.69	NS	NS

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Table 8. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on quality parameters of sugarcane

Treatments	Purity (%)				CCS (%)				Sugar yield (t/ha)				B:C ratio			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	92.28	92.39	92.18	92.29	12.60	12.55	12.50	12.55	18.76	18.16	16.12	17.68	3.23	3.03	2.34	2.87
S ₂	88.35	88.46	88.26	88.36	12.56	12.58	12.53	12.56	17.92	17.43	15.46	16.94	2.97	2.76	2.08	2.60
S ₃	87.90	88.01	87.81	87.91	12.58	12.51	12.47	12.52	17.84	17.25	15.31	16.80	2.64	3.03	2.12	2.60
S ₄	91.23	91.34	91.13	91.23	12.60	12.54	12.49	12.54	18.55	17.94	15.92	17.47	3.14	2.94	2.21	2.77
S ₅	78.83	78.93	78.75	78.84	12.41	12.26	12.21	12.29	15.79	15.15	13.45	14.79	2.28	2.06	1.27	1.87
Mean	87.72	87.83	87.63		12.55	12.54	12.44		17.77	17.25	15.24		2.83	2.62	1.90	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M				
SEd	0.63	0.87	1.44	2.97	0.09	0.12	0.21	0.42	0.12	0.17	0.27	0.57				
CD (5%)	4.04	3.33	NS	NS	0.57	0.47	NS	NS	0.77	0.64	NS	NS				

Table 9. Effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest sugarcane soil bulk density (Mg m⁻³)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	1.52				1.76				1.81			
S ₁ - FYM	1.40	1.41	1.41	1.41	1.64	1.65	1.70	1.66	1.69	1.70	1.79	1.73
S ₂ - CCP	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44	1.68	1.69	1.74	1.70	1.73	1.73	1.79	1.75
S ₃ - GM	1.45	1.46	1.45	1.45	1.70	1.70	1.75	1.72	1.75	1.75	1.79	1.76
S ₄ - PM	1.42	1.42	1.42	1.42	1.66	1.66	1.72	1.68	1.71	1.72	1.79	1.74
S ₅ - CST	1.47	1.48	1.48	1.48	1.71	1.71	1.75	1.72	1.77	1.78	1.80	1.78
Mean	1.44	1.44	1.44		1.68	1.68	1.73		1.73	1.74	1.79	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04
CD (5%)	NS	0.05	NS	NS	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.08

Table 10. Effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest sugarcane soil particle density (Mg m⁻³)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	2.69				2.73				2.77			
S ₁ - FYM	2.60	2.61	2.61	2.61	2.67	2.68	2.70	2.68	2.67	2.67	2.77	2.70
S ₂ - CCP	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.68	2.69	2.71	2.69	2.69	2.69	2.77	2.72
S ₃ - GM	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.69	2.69	2.71	2.70	2.69	2.69	2.77	2.72
S ₄ - PM	2.61	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.68	2.69	2.71	2.69	2.68	2.68	2.77	2.71
S ₅ - CST	2.62	2.63	2.63	2.63	2.69	2.70	2.73	2.71	2.71	2.71	2.77	2.73
Mean	2.61	2.62	2.62		2.68	2.69	2.71		2.69	2.69	2.77	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02
CD (5%)	NS	0.02	NS	NS	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04

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Table 11. Effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest sugarcane soil porosity (%)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	1.52				1.76				1.81			
S ₁ - FYM	46.15	45.98	45.98	46.04	38.58	38.43	37.04	38.02	36.94	36.57	35.38	36.30
S ₂ - CCP	45.04	45.04	45.04	45.04	37.31	37.17	35.79	36.76	35.69	35.69	35.38	35.58
S ₃ - GM	44.66	44.27	44.66	44.53	36.80	36.80	35.42	36.34	34.94	34.94	35.38	35.09
S ₄ - PM	45.59	45.80	45.80	45.73	38.06	38.29	36.53	37.63	36.19	35.82	35.38	35.80
S ₅ - CST	43.89	43.73	43.73	43.78	36.43	36.67	35.90	36.33	34.44	34.07	35.02	34.51
Mean	45.07	44.96	45.04		37.44	37.47	36.14		35.64	35.42	35.31	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.04	0.32	0.59	0.68	0.06	0.44	0.68	0.79	0.09	0.52	0.76	0.84
CD (5%)	NS	0.75	NS	NS	0.19	1.06	1.63	1.87	0.22	1.25	1.82	2.02

Table 12. Effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest sugarcane Soil Penetrometer reading (Psi)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	82.67				311.8				327.8			
S ₁ - FYM	61.55	61.74	62.18	61.82	180.8	182.2	301.4	221.5	198.6	199.2	322.6	240.1
S ₂ - CCP	67.25	67.78	68.25	67.76	206.5	208.4	304.6	239.8	222.4	222.8	323.4	256.2
S ₃ - GM	68.22	69.12	69.56	68.97	215.4	216.4	307.2	246.3	230.6	231.0	324.6	262.1
S ₄ - PM	65.46	65.86	66.14	65.82	192.5	193.4	303.8	229.9	211.2	212.8	322.8	248.9
S ₅ - CST	70.58	70.64	70.88	70.70	227.6	228.2	309.5	255.1	243.8	244.2	325.8	271.3
Mean	66.61	67.03	67.40		204.6	205.7	305.3		221.3	222.0	323.8	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.32	0.52	1.28	1.56	1.48	3.57	6.24	6.46	4.58	6.58	7.12	7.38
CD (5%)	NS	1.25	3.33	4.01	3.85	9.28	16.22	16.80	11.91	17.11	18.67	19.19

Table 13. Effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest sugarcane Soil Hydraulic Conductivity (cm hr⁻¹)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	1.30				0.12				0.11			
S ₁ - FYM	1.85	1.84	1.84	1.84	0.63	0.62	0.20	0.48	0.62	0.62	0.17	0.47
S ₂ - CCP	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.80	0.57	0.57	0.17	0.44	0.55	0.54	0.15	0.41
S ₃ - GM	1.76	1.75	1.74	1.75	0.53	0.52	0.17	0.41	0.52	0.51	0.14	0.39
S ₄ - PM	1.82	1.82	1.81	1.82	0.59	0.58	0.19	0.45	0.58	0.58	0.16	0.44
S ₅ - CST	1.73	1.72	1.71	1.72	0.51	0.51	0.16	0.39	0.50	0.50	0.14	0.38
Mean	1.79	1.79	1.78		0.57	0.56	0.18		0.55	0.55	0.15	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.07	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.08
CD (5%)	NS	0.07	NS	NS	0.08	0.11	0.13	0.16	0.11	0.13	0.18	0.21

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Table 14. Effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest sugarcane Soil Infiltration Rate (cm hr⁻¹)

Treatments	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	0.52			
S ₁ - FYM	0.76	0.75	0.58	0.70
S ₂ - CCP	0.71	0.70	0.56	0.66
S ₃ - GM	0.67	0.67	0.55	0.63
S ₄ - PM	0.73	0.73	0.57	0.68
S ₅ - CST	0.65	0.64	0.54	0.61
Mean	0.70	0.70	0.56	
	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.06
CD (5%)	0.05	0.07	0.12	0.14

Table 15. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on growth parameters of sugarcane

Treatments	Tillers ('000/ha)				Root dry weight (g/plant) @120 DAP				Root dry weight (g/plant) @ Harvest				Millable cane ('000/ha)			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	149.10	146.77	144.22	146.70	130.9	123.5	117.4	123.9	142.9	133.1	121.9	132.6	146.11	133.42	122.11	133.88
S ₂	143.21	140.96	138.52	140.90	125.7	118.6	112.8	119.0	137.3	127.9	117.1	127.4	140.33	128.14	117.28	128.58
S ₃	141.80	139.58	137.16	139.51	124.5	117.4	111.7	117.8	135.9	126.6	115.9	126.1	138.96	126.89	116.13	127.32
S ₄	146.02	143.73	141.23	143.66	128.2	120.9	115.0	121.3	139.9	130.4	119.3	129.9	143.08	130.66	119.58	131.11
S ₅	121.87	119.96	117.87	119.90	107.0	100.9	96.0	101.3	116.8	108.8	99.6	108.4	119.42	109.05	99.80	109.42
Mean	140.40	138.20	135.80		123.3	116.2	110.5		134.6	125.4	114.8		137.58	125.63	114.98	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.99	1.37	1.83	3.85	0.84	0.15	1.91	3.95	0.90	1.24	2.05	4.23	0.91	1.25	2.07	4.27
CD(5%)	6.35	5.25	7.04	8.98	5.37	4.43	NS	NS	5.74	4.75	NS	NS	5.80	4.79	NS	NS

Table 16. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on yield parameters of sugarcane

Treatments	Individual cane weight (kg)				Cane length (cm)				Cane girth (cm)				No. of nodes / cane			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	2.55	2.35	2.23	2.37	348.46	331.85	300.83	327.05	3.49	3.29	3.09	3.29	28.4	25.9	23.7	26.0
S ₂	2.44	2.25	2.14	2.27	333.62	317.72	288.02	313.12	3.34	3.15	2.96	3.15	27.2	24.8	22.7	24.9
S ₃	2.43	2.23	2.12	2.26	331.94	316.11	286.56	311.54	3.33	3.14	2.95	3.14	27.0	24.6	22.6	24.8
S ₄	2.52	2.32	2.20	2.35	344.49	328.07	297.40	323.32	3.45	3.26	3.06	3.26	28.1	25.6	23.5	25.7
S ₅	2.17	2.00	1.91	2.03	297.69	283.49	256.99	279.39	2.98	2.81	2.64	2.81	24.2	22.1	20.3	22.2
Mean	2.42	2.23	2.12		331.24	315.45	285.96		3.30	3.13	2.94		27.0	24.6	22.6	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.016	0.022	0.037	0.076	2.24	3.08	5.10	10.53	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.11	0.18	0.24	0.41	0.84
CD (5%)	0.104	0.086	NS	NS	14.30	11.81	NS	NS	0.14	0.12	NS	NS	1.14	0.94	NS	NS

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Table 17. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on yield parameters of sugarcane

Treat-ments	Internode length (cm)				Cane yield (t/ha)				Brix (%)				Pole (%)			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	12.6	12.1	11.4	12.0	143.3	129.9	118.6	130.6	23.73	22.54	22.53	22.93	18.98	17.33	17.57	17.96
S ₂	12.1	11.5	10.9	11.5	137.2	124.3	113.6	125.1	23.73	22.58	22.57	22.96	18.95	17.36	17.61	17.97
S ₃	12.0	11.5	10.9	11.5	136.5	123.7	113.0	124.4	23.61	22.47	22.46	22.84	18.93	17.28	17.52	17.91
S ₄	12.5	11.9	11.3	11.9	141.7	128.4	117.3	129.1	23.65	22.51	22.50	22.89	18.97	17.31	17.55	17.94
S ₅	10.8	10.3	9.8	10.3	122.5	110.9	101.4	111.6	23.08	22.01	22.00	22.36	18.62	16.92	17.16	17.57
Mean	12.0	11.5	10.9		136.3	123.4	112.8		23.56	22.42	22.41		18.89	17.24	17.48	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.08	0.11	0.19	0.39	0.89	1.23	2.13	4.16	0.16	0.23	0.37	0.77	0.13	0.18	0.29	0.61
CD (5%)	0.53	0.43	NS	NS	5.71	4.72	NS	NS	1.05	0.87	NS	NS	0.82	0.68	NS	NS

Table 18. Effect of mechanization on soil compaction and developing suitable management strategies on quality parameters of sugarcane

Treat-ments	Purity (%)				CCS (%)				Sugar yield (t/ha)				B:C ratio			
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	Mean
S ₁	84.35	80.89	82.06	82.43	12.47	11.13	11.38	11.66	17.88	14.45	13.50	15.28	4.22	2.88	2.02	3.04
S ₂	80.76	77.45	78.56	78.92	12.44	11.15	11.40	11.66	17.07	13.87	12.95	14.63	3.68	2.40	1.62	2.57
S ₃	80.35	77.06	78.16	78.52	12.45	11.10	11.34	11.63	17.00	13.73	12.82	14.52	3.07	2.87	1.68	2.54
S ₄	83.39	79.97	81.12	81.49	12.48	11.12	11.37	11.65	17.68	14.27	13.33	15.09	4.03	2.71	1.82	2.85
S ₅	72.06	69.11	70.10	70.42	12.29	10.87	11.11	11.42	15.05	12.06	11.26	12.79	2.47	1.30	0.55	1.44
Mean	80.18	76.90	78.00		12.43	12.54	11.32		16.93	15.48	12.77		3.46	2.19	1.39	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M				
SEd	0.56	0.78	1.29	2.65	0.08	0.11	0.20	0.39	0.10	0.14	0.25	0.49				
CD (5%)	3.60	2.98	NS	NS	0.53	0.44	NS	NS	0.67	0.55	NS	NS				

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Table 19. Residual effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest soil bulk density (Mg m^{-3})

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	1.52				1.76				1.81			
S ₁ - FYM	1.36	1.38	1.38	1.37	1.65	1.66	1.72	1.68	1.69	1.70	1.79	1.73
S ₂ - CCP	1.40	1.41	1.41	1.41	1.69	1.70	1.75	1.71	1.73	1.73	1.79	1.75
S ₃ - GM	1.41	1.43	1.42	1.42	1.71	1.71	1.76	1.73	1.75	1.75	1.79	1.76
S ₄ - PM	1.38	1.39	1.39	1.39	1.67	1.67	1.73	1.69	1.71	1.72	1.79	1.74
S ₅ - CST	1.43	1.45	1.45	1.44	1.72	1.72	1.76	1.73	1.77	1.78	1.80	1.78
Mean	1.36	1.38	1.38	1.37	1.69	1.69	1.74		1.73	1.74	1.79	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04
CD (5%)	NS	0.05	NS	NS	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.08

Table 20. Residual effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest soil particle density (Mg m^{-3})

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	2.69				2.73				2.77			
S ₁ - FYM	2.58	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.67	2.68	2.70	2.68	2.67	2.67	2.77	2.70
S ₂ - CCP	2.60	2.60	2.60	2.60	2.68	2.69	2.71	2.69	2.69	2.69	2.77	2.72
S ₃ - GM	2.60	2.60	2.60	2.60	2.69	2.69	2.71	2.70	2.69	2.69	2.77	2.72
S ₄ - PM	2.59	2.60	2.60	2.60	2.68	2.69	2.71	2.69	2.68	2.68	2.77	2.71
S ₅ - CST	2.60	2.61	2.61	2.61	2.69	2.70	2.73	2.71	2.71	2.71	2.77	2.73
Mean	2.59	2.60	2.60		2.68	2.69	2.71		2.69	2.69	2.77	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02
CD (5%)	NS	0.02	NS	NS	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04

Table 21. Residual effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest sugarcane soil porosity (%)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	1.52				1.76				1.81			
S ₁ - FYM	47.20	46.72	46.72	46.88	38.20	38.06	36.30	37.52	36.94	36.57	35.38	36.30
S ₂ - CCP	46.15	45.76	45.77	45.89	36.94	36.80	35.42	36.39	35.69	35.69	35.38	35.58
S ₃ - GM	45.77	45.00	45.38	45.38	36.43	36.43	35.06	35.97	34.94	34.94	35.38	35.09
S ₄ - PM	46.72	46.54	46.54	46.60	37.69	37.92	36.16	37.26	36.19	35.82	35.38	35.80
S ₅ - CST	45.00	44.44	44.44	44.63	36.06	36.30	35.53	35.96	34.44	34.07	35.02	34.51
Mean	46.17	45.69	45.77		37.06	37.10	35.69		35.64	35.42	35.31	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.04	0.30	0.58	0.66	0.05	0.41	0.63	0.76	0.09	0.52	0.76	0.84
CD (5%)	NS	0.75	NS	NS	0.17	0.98	1.52	1.82	0.22	1.25	1.82	2.02

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Table 22. Residual effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvests oil Penetrometer reading (Psi)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	82.67				311.8				327.8			
S ₁ - FYM	50.98	51.65	54.25	52.29	182.3	184.2	304.2	223.6	199.2	200.6	324.2	241.3
S ₂ - CCP	56.92	56.95	60.25	58.04	210.5	209.8	306.6	242.3	221.8	224.8	325.5	257.4
S ₃ - GM	58.78	59.05	61.51	59.78	218.2	217.4	310.2	248.6	232.6	233.6	326.4	264.2
S ₄ - PM	54.86	54.98	57.92	55.92	193.2	195.2	305.2	231.2	213.1	213.8	324.9	250.6
S ₅ - CST	61.04	61.25	63.10	61.70	228.7	229.9	310.9	256.5	245.2	245.8	326.2	272.4
Mean	56.52	56.84	59.35		206.6	207.3	307.4		222.4	223.7	266.6	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.28	0.47	1.19	1.36	1.48	3.57	6.24	6.46	4.60	6.61	7.28	7.49
CD (5%)	NS	1.25	3.09	3.54	3.85	9.28	16.22	16.80	11.96	17.19	18.93	19.47

Table 23. Residual effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest soil Hydraulic Conductivity (cm hr⁻¹)

Treatments	0 – 15 cm				15 – 30 cm				30 – 45 cm			
	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	1.30				0.12				0.11			
S ₁ - FYM	1.88	1.87	1.87	1.87	0.62	0.60	0.19	0.47	0.62	0.62	0.17	0.47
S ₂ - CCP	1.82	1.82	1.82	1.82	0.55	0.56	0.17	0.43	0.55	0.54	0.15	0.41
S ₃ - GM	1.79	1.72	1.72	1.74	0.51	0.50	0.16	0.39	0.52	0.51	0.14	0.39
S ₄ - PM	1.84	1.85	1.84	1.84	0.56	0.57	0.18	0.44	0.58	0.58	0.16	0.44
S ₅ - CST	1.72	1.74	1.73	1.73	0.51	0.51	0.15	0.39	0.50	0.50	0.14	0.38
Mean	1.81	1.80	1.80		0.55	0.55	0.17		0.55	0.55	0.15	
	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.08
CD (5%)	NS	0.05	NS	NS	0.08	0.13	0.14	0.19	0.10	0.12	0.16	0.21

Table 24. Residual effect of mechanized soil compaction management strategies on post harvest soil Infiltration rate (cm hr⁻¹)

Treatments	M ₁ -CP	M ₂ -DD	M ₃ -FP	Mean
Initial Soil	0.52			
S ₁ - FYM	0.77	0.76	0.59	0.71
S ₂ - CCP	0.70	0.69	0.55	0.65
S ₃ - GM	0.66	0.65	0.54	0.62
S ₄ - PM	0.74	0.74	0.58	0.69
S ₅ - CST	0.63	0.62	0.53	0.59
Mean	0.70	0.69	0.56	
	M	S	M x S	S x M
SEd	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.06
CD (5%)	0.05	0.07	0.11	0.15

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Fig. 1. Germination percentage

Fig.2. Sugarcane sprouting in ratoon crop ('000/ha)

Experimental Field Sub soil Compaction

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Core soil sampling Sub soil Compaction estimation

Infiltration Measurement

Chisel Plough Double disc Farmers practice (16" Single disc)